

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DINITROPHENYL KETONES AND PHENYLACETIC ACIDS. PART IV

By A. B. SEN AND P. M. BHARGAVA

2:4-Dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetone and 2:4-dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetic acid have been prepared by the ketonic and acid hydrolysis of 2:4-dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester. The ketone has been characterised by preparation of suitable derivatives. The reduction of 2:4-dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester by iron powder and water has also been carried out.

In the previous communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 268, 371; 1948, **25**, 282), 1-chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-bromobenzene, 1-chloro-2:6-dinitro-4-bromobenzene and 1-chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-iodobenzene have been condensed with acetoacetic ester and malonic ester, yielding the corresponding substituted acetoacetic and malonic esters, which on ketonic and acid hydrolysis yielded the corresponding phenylacetones and phenylacetic acids respectively. In this paper this reaction has been extended to 1:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene. 2:4-Dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester has also been reduced with iron powder and water to an indole derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:4-Dinitro-6-chlorophenol was obtained previously by the nitration of *o*-chlorophenol (Muller, *Arch. Phar.*, 1875, **203**, 111, 120; Faust and Muller, *Annalen*, 1876, **173**, 312, etc.). Exact experimental details being not available, it was obtained by the present authors in the following way.

o-Chlorophenol (15 g.) was added dropwise to an ice cooled mixture of nitric acid (conc., 51 c.c.) and water (17.1 c.c.) under continuous mechanical stirring. It was then heated with a low flame on a wire gauze till fumes of nitric acid ceased to be evolved. The mixture was then cooled, diluted with water and filtered. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, the phenol was obtained as a pale yellow crystalline substance, m.p. 113°, yield 24 g. (94.1% of theory).

2:4-Dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetoacetic Ester.—The sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester was prepared from acetoacetic ester (18 g.) and sodium (3 g.) in 50 c. c. of dry ether in a wetted-neck flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer and a reflux condenser. The flask was then cooled in ice and 1:6-dichloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene (14 g.), prepared from 2:4-dinitro-6-chlorophenol by the method of Ullmann and Sane (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 3731) added. The mixture was stirred in the cold for 2 hours and then refluxed on a water-bath for another 6 hours. Next day it was extracted with 2% caustic soda solution (300 c.c.); the aqueous extract was separated, cooled with ice and then acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a red oil separated. It was left in a refrigerator for 2 days, the supernatant aqueous layer was decanted off, the oil dissolved in cold alcohol, and the alcoholic solution filtered and left over for slow evaporation. After a few days the ester crystallised out in the form of light brown-red plates, m.p. 64°, yield 11.5 g. (59% of theory). (Found: N, 8.61. $C_{12}H_{11}O_7N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.47 per cent).

2:4-Dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetone.—The above ester (4 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (conc., 50 c.c.), and water (24 c.c.) was added to it without cooling with continuous stirring. After the evolution of CO_2 had ceased, the solution was poured on crushed ice and filtered. On recrystallisation of the crude ketone from hot alcohol, it was obtained as colourless crystals, m.p. 99° , yield theoretical. (Found: N, 10.63. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 10.48 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* of the above ketone was obtained by adding phenylhydrazine (1.5 c.c.) to a solution of the ketone (1 g.) in hot alcohol and refluxing for half an hour. The solution was cooled in ice, diluted with water, left in a refrigerator overnight and then filtered. On recrystallisation from hot alcohol, the phenylhydrazone was obtained as orange-red needles, m.p. 120° , yield 1.2 g. (91.1% of theory). (Found: N, 16.06. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{Cl}$ requires N, 15.86 per cent).

The *oxime* of the above ketone was obtained by dissolving the ketone (1.5 g.) in hot alcohol, cooling and adding to it hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.5 g.) followed by a drop of phenolphthalein and then caustic soda solution drop by drop, till the solution was alkaline to phenolphthalein. It was then refluxed for 1 hour, cooled, then poured in 50 c.c. of cold water and left in a refrigerator overnight. The supernatant liquid was decanted, the sticky mass dissolved in alcohol, the alcoholic solution filtered and the filtrate left over for slow evaporation, when fine, orange coloured crystals of the oxime were deposited, m.p. 95° , yield 1.1 g. (69.3% of theory). (Found: N, 15.19. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 15.32 per cent).

2:4-Dinitro-6-chlorophenylacetic Acid.—The ester (1 g.) was hydrolysed with 20% alcoholic potash (12 c.c.) to which water (1 c.c.) had been added, on a water-bath for 1 hour. The alcohol was then distilled off, the residue cooled, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, allowed to stand in a refrigerator overnight and then filtered. The product was dissolved in hot alcohol, filtered and the filtrate left over for slow evaporation, when the acid crystallised out as a dark brown powder. It does not melt, but decomposes on heating strongly, yield 0.7 g. (38.8% of theory). (Found: N, 10.45. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 10.75 per cent).

2-Methyl 3-carboxyethyl-5-iodo-7-aminoindole.—The ester (1.6 g.), iron powder (3 g.), crystallised ferrous sulphate (0.3 g.) and water (10 c.c.) were refluxed for 3 hours and then cooled with stirring in ice. It was then filtered, the residue extracted with boiling alcohol, the extract filtered hot, and the filtrate allowed to evaporate by itself when fine brown needles of the reduction product were obtained, m.p. $126-27^\circ$ (decomp.), yield 0.7 g. (57.3% of theory). (Found: N, 10.74. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3\text{Cl}$ requires N, 11.09 per cent).

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